

Determination of Abnormalities of Prothrombin Time (PT) and Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (APTT) in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) and Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA)

Junali Tikhak¹, Rachel Shimray², Sharmila Laishram³, Soram Gayatri Gatphoh⁴, O. Okendrajit Singh⁵, M. Reeta Devi⁶

¹Medical Officer, District Hospital, District - Changling, Arunachal Pradesh.

²Assistant Professor, Pathology Department, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, RIMS, Imphal.

³Associate Professor, Pathology Department, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, RIMS, Imphal.

⁴Assistant Professor, Pathology Department, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, RIMS, Imphal.

⁵Professor, Pathology Department, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, RIMS, Imphal.

⁶Professor, Pathology Department, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, RIMS, Imphal.

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Soram Gayatri Gatphoh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) and Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) are both chronic inflammatory diseases of autoimmune origin. They are both characterized by the presence of autoantibodies such as ANA and antiphospholipid antibodies among others. Some of these antibodies interfere with in vitro clotting tests and predispose to thrombosis and can lead to complications. In the present study, PT, APTT and mixing tests were done which are simple tests to determine if any coagulation abnormality exists in SLE and RA patients and to assess any role of inhibitors in the group of these patients with altered PT and aPTT.

Material and Methods: The present study was for a period of 2 years. A total of 72 diagnosed cases of SLE and RA irrespective of age were included in the study. SLE and RA patients with co-existing connective tissue diseases and other autoimmune diseases were excluded. Relevant demographic and clinical data like age, sex, weight, height, relevant personal history and provisional diagnosis were obtained. Complete hemogram (haemoglobin, total leucocyte count, haematocrit MCV, MCH, MCHC, platelet count differential leucocyte count, ESR), Prothrombin Time (PT), Activated partial thromboplastin (aPTT) were performed in all the cases. Mixing studies were performed whenever indicated.

Result: Out of a total of 74 patients included in the study, majority were females (89.2%, n=66). Maximum number of patients were seen to belong to the age group 31-40 years (27%, n=20) followed by age groups 21-30 years and 41-50 years (20.3%, n=15). Majority of the patients in both males and females had mild anemia i.e., 62.5% (n=5) and 41.9% (n=31), respectively. In case of SLE patients, Majority (82.5%, n=47) showed normal PT and only 17.5% (n=10) participants show prolonged prothrombin time. Majority of SLE patients (86%, n=49) had normal aPTT and only 8 out of 57 (14%) show prolonged aPTT. In case of rheumatoid arthritis patients, only 4 (23.5%) patients had prolonged prothrombin time (>16 seconds) and showed a mean of 13.9 ± 2.7 seconds and majority (88.2%, n=15) of them had normal aPTT and only 2 out of 17 (11.8%) show prolonged aPTT. Only 2 (20%) out of 10 patients showed prolonged prothrombin time after mixing test among SLE patients whereas 2 (50%) out of 4 patients showed prolonged prothrombin time after mixing test among RA patients. 5 (37.5%) out of 8 participants show prolonged aPTT even after mixing test in SLE patients and all of 2 (100%) patients with prolonged activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) were corrected after mixing test in RA patients.

Conclusion: Our study showed 91.2% of SLE and 82.5% of RA patients as female. Out of the total, prolonged PT was seen 17.5% of patients in SLE and 23.5% in RA and prolonged APTT was seen in 14% of the SLE patients and 11.8% of RA patients. Nevertheless, thromboembolic events when they occur, can be life-threatening and mixing tests not correcting the prolonged clotting times should raise high degree of suspicion for diagnosis of circulating factor inhibitor or anticoagulant. Those patients with persisting prolonged clotting times could be followed up to note if any thromboembolic or hemorrhagic events occur in the future and correlate with the abnormal coagulation profile.

Keywords: Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), Rheumatoid arthritis (RA), Prothrombin time (PT), Activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT).

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) is an autoimmune disease involving multiple organs characterized by a vast array of autoantibodies, particularly antinuclear antibodies (ANAs) in which injury is caused mainly by deposition of immune complexes and binding of antibodies to various cells and tissues. SLE is a fairly common disease, with a prevalence that may be as high as 1 in 2500 in certain populations. Similar to many autoimmune diseases, SLE predominantly affects women with a female: male ratio of 9:1 during the reproductive age group of 17-55 years. The hallmark of SLE is the production of autoantibodies such as antinuclear antibodies and antiphospholipid antibodies. Antinuclear antibodies (ANAs) are directed against nuclear antigens and can be grouped into four categories: antibodies to DNA, antibodies to histones, antibodies to non-histone proteins bound to RNA and antibodies to nucleolar antigens. Antiphospholipid antibodies are autoantibodies which react with epitopes on proteins which are revealed when they are in a complex with phospholipids. They are present in 30-40% of Lupus patients. Included among these proteins are prothrombin, annexin V, beta2 glycoprotein, protein S and protein C. Some of these antibodies interfere with *in vitro* clotting tests, such as partial thromboplastin time. Therefore, these antibodies are sometimes referred to as Lupus anticoagulant (LAC). [1] LAC is the most common circulating anticoagulant in hemostatically normal people. [2] It causes prolongation of clotting tests *in vitro* but predisposes more to thrombosis than haemorrhage. [2,3]

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory disorder of autoimmune origin that may affect many tissues and organs but principally attacks the joints, producing a non-suppurative, proliferative and inflammatory synovitis. Extra-articular lesions may involve skin, heart, blood vessels and lungs and therefore, the clinical manifestations can resemble other autoimmune disorders such as SLE or Scleroderma. The disease peaks in the second to fourth decades and is three times more common in women than men [1] Different types of autoantibodies can be detected in the serum of patients with RA [4] Several types of antiphospholipid antibodies widely used in diagnosis of antiphospholipid antibody syndrome (APS) include lupus anticoagulant, anticardiolipin antibodies and anti-beta 2 glycoprotein I antibodies. [5] These antibodies may occur not only in APS but also in other disorders, particularly in connective tissue diseases, other autoimmune diseases, infections, neoplasms, and as a result of drug use. In literature, the estimated prevalence of antiphospholipid antibody in RA patients varies from 4% to 49%, with average prevalence of 28%

and median prevalence of 22%, based on the data collected from several studies. [6] The pathologic changes are mediated by antibodies against self-antigens and cytokine mediated inflammation, predominantly secreted by CD4+ T cells. [1]

The common causes of a prolonged PT are administration of an oral anticoagulant drug, presence of a direct acting inhibitor of factor Xa, liver disease, particularly obstructive jaundice, vitamin K deficiency, Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation and rarely, deficiency of factor VII, X, or prothrombin or prothrombin defect. Common causes of a prolonged APTT are Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation, liver disease, transfusion with plasma-depleted red blood cells, administration of or contamination with heparin or other anticoagulants, a non-specific circulating anticoagulant e.g LAC, the presence of a direct acting anticoagulant drugged anti-IIa, anti-Xa agents, deficiency of coagulation factors other than factor VII. Circulating anticoagulants or acquired inhibitors of coagulation factors are immunoglobulins arising either in congenitally deficient individuals as a result of the administration of the missing factor or in previously hemostatically normal subjects as part of an autoimmune process. Usually, an inhibitor is suspected when a prolonged clotting test does not correct after mixing 50:50 with normal plasma or if an apparent factor deficiency does not fit with a patient's clinical history. Antibodies to factor VIII causes bleeding tendency. It is found in hemophiliacs as well as, as autoantibodies in previously normal individuals. In hemophiliacs, the complex of factor VIII and antibody to factor VIII has no factor VIII activity while in previously normal individuals, the Ag-Ab complex has residual FVIII activity. The target of antiphospholipid syndrome (APS) is not only isolated phospholipids but phospholipid-binding proteins namely beta2 glycoprotein 1 and prothrombin. Several groups investigated the clinical significance of anti-prothrombin antibodies in patients with anti-phospholipid syndrome or SLE and there is evidence that these antibodies are involved in the occurrence of thromboembolic events and pregnancy loss in the course of APS [3,7,8] Anti-PT antibodies were observed in patients with SLE and APS with an incidence ranging from 7% to 46% [9,10] The natural history of patients with SLE can be complicated by thromboembolic accidents which range from 4.5 - 18% of cases, while miscarriages have been reported to occur in 16% of such patients. [11-13] Other studies however have shown a higher incidence of clinical events related to thrombosis in SLE [14,15]

Aims and Objects:

1. To determine abnormalities of Prothrombin Time (PT) and Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (aPTT) in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) and Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) patients
2. To assess any role of inhibitors in patients of SLE and RA with altered PT and aPTT.

Materials and Methods

A hospital based cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Pathology in collaboration with Department of Medicine, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal for a period of 2 years (September 2019 to August 2021). Diagnosed cases of SLE and RA irrespective of age, were included in the study. SLE and RA with co-existing connective tissue diseases and other autoimmune diseases were excluded. Relevant demographic and clinical data like age, sex, weight, height, relevant personal history, provisional diagnosis were obtained. All together 72 cases were chosen to participate in the study. Complete hemogram (haemoglobin, total leucocyte count, haematocrit, MCV, MCH, MCHC, platelet count, Differential leucocyte count, ESR), Prothrombin Time (PT), Activated partial thromboplastin (aPTT) were performed in all the cases. Mixing studies were performed whenever indicated.

Operational definitions**1.) Prothrombin Time:**

Principle: Tissue Thromboplastin in the presence of calcium activates the extrinsic pathway of human blood coagulation mechanism. When thromboplastin reagent is added to normal anticoagulated plasma, the clotting mechanism is initiated, forming a solid gel clot within a specified period of time.²³ The time required for clot formation would be prolonged if there is a deficiency of factors or factor activity in the extrinsic pathway of the coagulation mechanism.

Normal value: 11 to 16 seconds

PT INR: For standardization and to obtain comparable results, it is recommended to report PT in the form of International Normalised Ratio (INR)

$INR = \frac{PT \text{ of patient}}{PT \text{ of control}}^{ISI}$ where ISI=International Sensitivity Index of the reagent used.

2.) Activated Partial Thromboplastin (aPTT):

Principle: aPTT measures the clotting time of plasma after activation of contact factors and the addition of phospholipid and Calcium chloride (CaCl₂) but without added tissue thromboplastin and so, indicates the overall efficiency of the intrinsic pathway. The plasma is first pre-incubated for a set period with a contact activator such as kaolin, silica or ellagic acid. During this phase, activated factor XII (FXIIa) is produced which cleaves factor XI to factor XIa. But coagulation does not proceed beyond this point in the absence of calcium. After re-calcification, activated FXI activates FIX and coagulation follows. A standardized phospholipid is provided to allow the test to be performed on PPP (Platelet poor plasma). The test depends not only on the factors VIII and IX but also on the reactions with factors X, V, prothrombin and fibrinogen. It is also sensitive to the presence of circulating anticoagulants (inhibitors) and heparin.

Normal value : 26 to 40 seconds

3) Mixing test:

Principle: Simple correction tests done by mixing the patients's plasma with normal plasma. If the prolongation of PT and aPTT is due to deficiency of a clotting factor, the PT or APTT should return to within a few seconds of normal, whereas failure to correct suggests the presence of an inhibitor.

Study tools: 1) Pre-test proforma

2) Hemostasis analyser Manufacturing company: Tulip Diagnostics, Goa, India

Model no. Hemostar XF 1.0

3) Reagents: Liquiplastin (thromboplastin derived from rabbit brain)

Calcium Chloride

Kaolin

Phospholipid

3.2% Trisodium Citrate

4) Platelet Poor Plasma (PPP) from patients and controls

Result

Out of a total of 74 patients included in the study, majority were females (89.2%, n=66).

Figure 1: Distribution of the patients by sex (N=74)

Table 1: Age wise Distribution of cases patients according to age (N=74)

Age (years)	n	%
<10	2	2.7
11-20	10	13.5
21-30	15	20.3
31-40	20	27.0
41-50	15	20.3
51-60	8	10.8
>60	4	5.4
Total	74	100

Maximum number of patients were seen to belong to inthe age group 31-40 years (27%, n=20) followed by age groups 21-30 years and 41-50 years (20.3%, n=15). The least number of participants were from age group <10 years (2.7%, n=2).

Table 2: Distribution of level of hemoglobin based on gender (N=74)

Category	Males	n (%)	Females	n (%)	Total	Mean \pm SD
Severe	<7	0	<7	3 (4.5)	2 (2.7)	10.3 \pm 1.7
Moderate	7-10	2 (25)	7-10	22 (33.3)	18 (24.3)	
Mild	10-13	5 (62.5)	10-12	32 (48.5)	31 (41.9)	
normal	>13	1 (12.5)	>12	9 (13.6)	5 (6.70)	

The mean haemoglobin% of all the patients (N=74) was 10.3 \pm 1.7 which ranged from 6.3gm% to 16.3gm%. Majority of the patients in both males and females had mild anemia i.e., 62.5% (n=5) and 41.9% (n=31), respectively.

Table 3 : Distribution of participants by Prothrombin time (PT) abnormality in SLE patients (N=57)

Prothrombin time (PT) (seconds)	n (%)	Mean \pm SD
Normal PT (11-16)	47 (82.5)	14.90 \pm 4.3
Prolonged PT (>16)	10 (17.5)	

Majority (82.5%, n=47) of participants showed normal PT. Only 17.5% (n=10) participants show prolonged prothrombin time. The mean of prothrombin time is 14.90 \pm 4.3 seconds ranges from 10 to 28 seconds.

Table 4 : Distribution of the participants based on activated Partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) in SLE patients (N=57)

Activated Partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) (seconds)	n (%)	Mean \pm SD
<40	49 (86)	32.26 \pm 6.30
>40	8 (14)	

Majority (86%, n=49) of participants had normal aPTT and only 8 out of 57 (14%) show prolonged aPTT. The mean value of activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (aPTT) is 32.26 \pm 6.30 (mean \pm SD) seconds which ranges from 26 to 48 seconds.

Table 5: Distribution of participants by Prothrombin time (PT) abnormality in RA patients (N=17)

Prothrombin time (PT) (seconds)	n (%)	Mean ± SD
Normal PT (11-16)	13 (76.5)	13.9 ± 2.7
Prolonged PT (>16)	4 (23.5)	

Only 4 (23.5%) patients had prolonged prothrombin time (>16 seconds) and showed a mean of 13.9 ± 2.7 seconds.

Table 6 : Distribution of the participants based on activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) in RA patients (N=17)

Activated Partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) (seconds)	n (%)	Mean ±SD
≤40	15 (88.2)	28.41 ± 5.4
>40	2 (11.8)	

Majority (88.2%, n=15) of participants had normal aPTT and only 2 out of 17 (11.8%) show prolonged aPTT. The mean value of activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (aPTT) is 28.41 ± 5.4 (mean ± SD) seconds which ranges from 26 to 43 seconds.

Figure 2: Distribution of patients with prolonged prothrombin time (PT) after mixing test in SLE and RA patients (N=24)

Only 2 (20%) out of 10 patients showed prolonged prothrombin time after mixing test among SLE patients whereas 2 (50%) out of 4 patients showed prolonged prothrombin time after mixing test among RA patients.

Figure 3: Distribution of patients with prolonged activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) after mixing test in SLE and RA patients (N=15)

Figure 3: Distribution of patients with prolonged activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) after mixing test in SLE and RA patients (N=15)

5 (37.5%) out of 8 participants show prolonged aPTT even after mixing test in SLE patients and all of 2 (100%) patients with prolonged activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) were corrected after mixing test in RA patients.

Discussion

Systemic Lupus Erythematosus is the prototype of systemic autoimmune diseases. The clinical presentation and severity in individual patients may vary considerably and therefore treatment strategies need to be tailored accordingly.[16]Our study

showed predominance of female patients (89.2%), as in the study by Malaviya AN et al.[17] A study by Chen JL et al [18] showed 52.1% had anemia, whereas our study showed 62.5% of males and 41.9% of female patients with SLE as having anemia, from mild to severe degree, the variation in findings could be due to geographical difference. In a study by Moore et al [19], only 17 (4.3%) out of 400 patients had prolonged PT in the presence of Lupus anticoagulant. Similarly, in our study, 14% of SLE and 23.5% of RA cases showed prolonged PT, the higher percentage of cases with prolonged PT could be attributed to a small sample size (74 cases) and geographical variation or difference in ethnicity of the population studied. A study by Al Dhanhani AM et al[20] showed the mean (-SD) age at the time of diagnosis was 28.6 – 12.4 years which is comparable to our study wherein the age group most affected was 31- 40 years. In a study done by Saraya AK et al,[21] 7.3% patients had prolonged PT and 32.7% (N = 55) of patients with SLE had abnormal APTT whereas in our study (N=57), 21% had prolonged PT and 11.6% had prolonged APTT, the difference could be due to small sample size and short duration of our study. In our study of RA patients, majority (82.5%) of patients were females, similar to studies by Mohammed A et al [22] and Han C et al[23], Eshmrzaeva A et al [24]

Our study detected anaemia in 70.6% of RA patients similar to various studies [25,26,27, 28,29,30] which showed 30% – 70% of RA patients to be anaemic. However, a higher percentage of 84% were found to be anemic in a study by Kumari DM et al [31]. Prolonged PT was seen in 23.5% of patients and prolonged APTT was seen in 11.8% of patients of RA among a total of 17 in the present study. APTT was shortened in 16.6% and PT was abnormal in 6.67% of patients in a study by Zhang P et al [32]. The dissimilarity in findings could be due to geographical differences or ethnicity difference. Our study however showed majority (82.5% for PT and 86% for aPTT) of the patients had normal PT and aPTT. In our study, mixing tests corrected 80% and 50% of prolonged PT in SLE and RA respectively. 37.5% of SLE cases with abnormal aPTT remained abnormal after mixing tests. PT and APTT may get corrected despite the presence of inhibitor because of dilution and the mild inhibitor maybe masked. Seethala S et al.[33] reported individual cases of bleeding abnormalities in patients with SLE having factor deficiencies and circulating inhibitor.

The main disadvantage of mixing tests is that it does not permit 100% differentiation of factor deficiency versus factor inhibitors. Results of prolonged APTT and the result persisting after mixing test should raise a high index of suspicion in such cases.

Conclusion

In the present study, PT, APTT and mixing tests were done which are simple tests to determine if any coagulation abnormality exists in the SLE and RA patients. In keeping with its epidemiology of affecting females more, our study showed 91.2% of SLE and 82.5% of RA patients as female. Out of the total, prolonged PT was seen 17.5% of patients in SLE and 23.5% in RA and prolonged APTT was seen in 14% of the SLE patients and 11.8% of RA patients. Nevertheless, thromboembolic events when they occur, can be life-threatening and mixing tests not correcting the prolonged clotting times should raise high degree of suspicion for diagnosis of circulating factor inhibitor or anticoagulant. Due to paucity of cases during the study period due to ongoing Corona virus pandemic, sample size was limited to 74 and that affected the results of the study. Those patients with persisting prolonged clotting times could be followed up to note if any thromboembolic or hemorrhagic events occur in the future and correlate with the abnormal coagulation profile.

References

1. Kumar A, Abbas AK, Aster Jon C editors. Robbins and Cotran Pathologic Basis of Disease. 9thed. Philadelphia: Elsevier;2018.
2. Bain BJ, Bates I, Laffan MA, Lewis SM. Dacie and Lewis Practical Haematology.12th ed. Elsevier; 2017.
3. Love PE, Santoro SA. Antiphospholipid antibodies: anticardiolipin and the lupus anticoagulant in systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) and in non-SLE disorders. Prevalence and clinical significance. *Ann Intern Med* 1990;112(9): 682-98.
4. Olech E, Merrill JT. The prevalence and clinical significance of antiphospholipid antibodies in rheumatoid arthritis. *Curr Rheumatoid Rep* 2006 Apr; 8:100-8.
5. Filipowicz SA, Rupinski R, Walewska E. The prevalence and clinical significance of antiphospholipid antibodies in rheumatoid arthritis. *Pol Arch Med Wewn* 2007; 117: 33-8.
6. Levine JS, Brandon DW, Ranc J. The antiphospholipid syndrome. *N Eng J Med* 2002 Mar 7; 346(10):752-63.
7. Atsumi T, Koike T. Clinical relevance of anti-prothrombin antibodies. *Autoimmune Rev* 2002 Feb;1(1-2):49-53.
8. Simmelink MJ, Horbach DA, Derksen RHM, Meijers JC, Bevers EM, Willems GM et al. Complexes of anti-prothrombin antibodies and prothrombin cause lupus anticoagulant activity by competing with the binding of clotting factors for catalytic phospholipid surfaces. *Br J Haematol* 2001 Jun;113(3):621-9.
9. von Landenberg P, Matthias T, Zaech J, Schultz M, Larber M, Blank M et al. Anti-prothrombin

- antibodies are associated with pregnancy loss in patients with the antiphospholipid syndrome. *Am J Reprod Immunol* 2003 Jan;49(1);51-6.
10. Nojima J, Kratsune H, Suehisa E, Futsukaichi Y, Yamanishi H, Machii T et al. Anti-prothrombin antibodies combined with lupus anticoagulant activity is an essential risk factor for venous thromboembolism in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Br J Haematol* 2001 Sept; 114(3):647-54
 11. Angles-Cano E, Sultan Y, Clavel JP. predisposing factors to thrombosis in systemic lupus erythematosus. *J Lab Clin Med* 1979 Aug 94(2): 312-23.
 12. Prentice RL, Gatenby PA, Loblay RH, Shearman RP, Kronenberg H, Basten A. Lupus anticoagulant in pregnancy. *Lancet*. 1984 Aug; 2(8400):464.
 13. Ramsey-Goldman R. Pregnancy in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Rheum Dis Clin North Am*. 1988 Apr;14(1):169-85.
 14. Derksen RH WM, Bouma BN, Kater L. The striking association between lupus anticoagulant and fetal loss in systemic lupus erythematosus patients. *Arthritis Rheum*, 1986; 29:695-6.
 15. Boey ML, Colaco CB, Gharavi AE, Elkon KB, Loizou S, Hughes GRV. Thrombosis in systemic lupus erythematosus: striking association with the presence of circulating lupus anticoagulant. *Br Med J*. 1983 Oct ;287(6398):1021-3.
 16. Kumar A. Indian guidelines on the management of SLE. *J Indian Rheumatol Assoc*, 2002; 10:80-96.
 17. Malaviya AN, Singh RR, Singh YN, Kapoor SK, Kumar A. Prevalence of systemic lupus erythematosus in India. *Lupus*. 1993 Apr; 2(2):115-8.
 18. Chen JL, Huang XM, Zeng XJ, Wang Y, Zhou MX, Ma YH, Li RS, Shen T. Hematological abnormalities in systemic lupus erythematosus and clinical significance thereof: comparative analysis of 236 cases. *Zhonghuayixuezhazhi*. 2007 May 1;87(19):1330-3.
 19. Moore GW, Rangarajan S, Holland LJ, Henley A, Savidge GF. Low frequency of elevated prothrombin times in patients with lupus anticoagulants when using a recombinant thromboplastin reagent: implications for dosing and monitoring of oral anticoagulant therapy. *Br J Biomed Sci*. 2005 Jan 1; 62 (1): 15-8.
 20. Al Dhanhani AM, Agarwal M, Othman YS, Bakoush O. Incidence and prevalence of systemic lupus erythematosus among the native Arab population in UAE. *Lupus*. 2017 May; 26 (6): 664-9.
 21. Saraya AK, Rai R, Saxena R, Singh RR, Padmakumark, Malaviya AN. Coagulation abnormalities in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus. *Indian J Med Res* 1989 Oct; 90:335-40.
 22. Mohammad A, Alshamari T, Adeye T, Lazariu V, Mc Nutt LA, Caroenter DO. A comparison of risk factors for osteo and rheumatoid arthritis using NHANES data. *Prev. Med. Rep*. 2020 Dec 1; 20: 101242.
 23. Han C, Zhao N, Rahman MU, Doyle MK, Bala MV. A case-control study of anaemia in patients with rheumatoid arthritis treated with disease modifying antirheumatic drugs in an adult population in the US: prevalence and impact on healthcare utilization. *J Med Econ*. 2008 Jan 1; 11 (2): 255- 64.
 24. Eshmurzaeva A, Karimov M, Mavlyanov I, Sibirkin M, Tukhtaeva N, Abdullaev B. The incidence of Anaemia in Patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis. *J Adv Med Res*. 2016 Feb 22-7.
 25. Ganna S. The prevalence of anemia in rheumatoid arthritis. *Rev Bras reumatol*. 2014 Jul; 54: 257 -9.
 26. Vreugdenhil G, Wognum AW, Van Eijik HG, Swaak AJG. Anemia in rheumatoid arthritis: the role of iron, vitamin B12, folic acid deficiency and erythropoietin responsiveness. *Ann Rheum Dis* 1990; 49: 93 -8.
 27. Hansen NE. The anemia of chronic disorders: a bag of unresolved questions. *Scand J Haematol*. 1983; 31: 397 – 402.
 28. Baer AN, Dessypris EN, Krantz SB. The pathogenesis of anemia in rheumatoid arthritis: a clinical and laboratory analysis. *Semin Arthritis Rheum*. 1990; 19: 209 -23.
 29. Remacha AF, Rodriguez-de la Serna A, Garcia-Die F, Geli C. Erythroid abnormalities in rheumatoid arthritis: the role of erythropoietin. *J Rheumatol*. 1992; 19: 1687 -97.
 30. Peeters HRM, Jongen-Lavrence M, Raja AN, et al. Course and characteristics of anemia in patients of rheumatoid arthritis of recent onset. *Ann Rheum Dis*. 1996; 55 :162-8.
 31. Kumari DM. Study of anemia in rheumatoid arthritis. *Int J Dev. Res*. 2018;8 (05): 20568 -72.
 32. Zhang P, Liu J, Tan B. Hypercoagulation in Patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis Correlates with Activation of Act1/ NF-KB Signalling Pathway. *J Rheum Dis Treat*. 2015; 1: 024.
 33. Seethala S, Collins NP Jr, Comerchi G Jr. An unusual etiology for elevation of activated partial thromboplastin time in SLE: acquired haemophilia and lupus anticoagulant. *Case Rep Hematol*. 2013.